

Research-in-Progress Paper

The role of urban Living Labs in knowledge transfer and replication of experimental solutions for urban proximity

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Abstract

This study investigates the role of Urban Living Labs (ULLs) in facilitating knowledge transfer and replicating experimental solutions for urban proximity, drawing on experiences from Finland, Switzerland, Italy, Spain, Belgium, Netherlands and Turkey. The primary aim is to analyse the methodologies and activities through which ULLs contribute to the dissemination and adoption of urban experiments by follower cities across Europe, ensuring the transfer of knowledge and the spread of innovative solutions across diverse regions and contexts. ULLs are examined as spaces for open innovation, knowledge transfer and the replication of experimental methodologies and tools, particularly within the framework of sustainable mobility and urban proximity, as envisioned by the 15-minute city concept. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, including literature analysis, in-depth semi-structured interviews, and case study design. Data analysis involves descriptive individual and comparative cross-case analysis, as well as mapping of solutions and practices for replication. The findings are expected to highlight the potentials and challenges of ULLs in knowledge transfer and the replication of experimental solutions for urban mobility and proximity. Recommendations and an actionable framework will be provided to diverse stakeholders to promote sustainable urban transitions and replicate successful experimental solutions through ULLs.

Key words

Urban Living Labs, experimentation, urban proximity, interactive tools, knowledge transfer, replication

Introduction and background

Urban Living Labs (ULLs) have emerged as geographically embedded platforms for co-creating, testing, learning and implementing innovative interventions and processes (Bulkeley et al, 2019; Voitenko et al., 2016). Bringing together diverse stakeholders, and proposing open arenas for exchange, sharing and experimentation, ULLs allow to collaboratively address complex societal challenges such as urban and climate transitions (Evans, Karvonen & Raven, 2016). In this regard, the overall aim of ULLs is to experiment and test innovative solutions, by integrating different stakeholders and contributing to creation of transformative capacity building programmes (Dvarionienė, Dvarionas, & Kamičaitytė, 2023).

Experimentation is a promising way of approaching governance and implementation of sustainability transitions (Von Wirth et al., 2019; Sengers, Wieczorek, & Raven, 2016). Moreover, recent research has shown potential of ULLs – as arenas for experimentation – to contribute to the development of actionable tools, innovative methodologies, as well as to propose governance models (Kronsell & Mukhtar-Landgren, 2018; Bullkeley et al., 2016). Learning and experimenting in real-life urban context refer to the production and exchange of knowledge among participants (Marvin et al., 2018). Thus, the aim is not only to learn from the specific experiences, but also to replicate the innovations creating potentials for acceleration of relevant solutions and proposing environment for emerging smart solutions (Ruess & Lindner, 2023). This specific emphasis on knowledge production, documentation and transfer distinguishes ULLs from policy experiments or innovation niches (Evans & Karvonen, 2014).

Replication is highlighted as one of key defining characteristics of ULLs (Steen & Van Bueren, 2017). A considerable amount of research is carried out around the characteristics, tools, innovative solutions and co-creating experiences of ULLs (Florez Ayala, Alberton & Ersoy, 2022). However, the focus on replication needs particular attention, becoming one of the central elements of further integration into the policies and decision-making procedures on local, national and international levels. Analysing replication potentials and mechanisms in ULLs is becoming even more relevant considering the urgent challenges and call from politics and academia to propose actionable ways of addressing and accelerating dissemination of good practices between several hundred cities according to Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2015; Schot & Steinmueller, 2016), as well as highlighted by such programmes as Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy (Covenant of Mayors, 2021; Rivas, Urraca & Bertoldi, 2022), Carbon Neutral Cities Alliance (CNCA, 2021; Huovila et al., 2022) and C40 Cities (C40, 2023).

Urban mobility field represents a significant challenge for urban and climate transitions, being one of the main sources of CO2 emissions. Regarding the aims of scaling up innovations both at local and European levels, the need for new practical solutions is evident. The concept of ULLs is

particularly relevant in the context of sustainable mobility, where the need for innovative and scalable solutions is critical to achieving sustainability goals and ensuring equal distribution of innovations across urban areas (Shibayama & Emberger, 2023).

One of the broadly promoted concepts to approach challenges of urban transition, sustainable proximity and experimental solutions is the **15-minute City** (Moreno, 2024). This concept envisions integration of diverse services all accessible within a 15-minute walk or bike ride allowing better connectivity, inclusivity and resilience (Moreno et al., 2021). This model is frequently discussed by research and political actors as a promising path to reshape cities. At the same time, it's facing criticism for implementation issues as well as its descent with cities' challenges (Gerten & Fina, 2022).

Both ULLs and 15-minute City concepts promote the co-creation of urban environment with regards to diversity and accessibility as well as bottom-up initiatives. **Converging these two models** seems to have potential in opening new perspectives on their opportunities and challenges addressing replication of innovative solutions in urban areas. Previous studies have shown the effectiveness of ULLs in various domains, including citizen participation, integration of art into the urban landscape and co-creation of public spaces. They also ensure active engagement of diverse stakeholders into strategic urban planning processes, such as Sustainable Energy and Climate action plans (SECAPs) or Sustainable Urban Mobility plans (SUMP).

Extensive research has been conducted on **the characteristics and benefits of ULLs** as platforms that facilitate innovation in both the public and private sectors (Fuglsang et al., 2021; Steen, Kris & Ellen Van Bueren, 2017). **The transformative changes of complex urban environments require clear replication methodologies and guidance** in relation to urban transition and successful practices accumulated by the ULLs around Europe and beyond. In this context, research has increasingly pointed to the importance of experimentation, calling for flexible, dynamic and adaptable governance models and open approaches (Kuhlmann & Rip, 2014; Scholl, de Kraker & Dijk, 2022). Despite their proliferation in different fields, it is **still largely unstudied whether and how ULLs contribute to broader dissemination through experimental solutions and practices. It lacks deeper understanding of specific mechanisms, potential and challenges of**

ULLs for replication and effective knowledge transfer. This paper aims to address these gaps by analysing:

- To what extent do the ULLs provide opportunities for sharing knowledge and replicating experimental solutions?
- What are the existing practices, promising methods and tools allowing to replicate urban solutions, focusing on sustainable urban mobility and proximity (15-minute City)?
- Through which mechanisms could the ULLs contribute to connect local initiatives with global strategies and networks?
- What use-cases and practices from the ULLs illustrate examples of replicating solutions for urban proximity and sustainable mobility?

Methodology

This study uses a mixed-methods approach to explore how ULLs facilitate knowledge transfer and the replication of experimental solutions for sustainable mobility. Combining qualitative and quantitative techniques, the methodology ensures a comprehensive understanding of the research questions (Savin-Baden & Major, 2023). Data will be analysed through descriptive case studies, cross-case comparisons (Borman et al., 2012), and solution mapping to identify replicable practices and patterns.

Table 1. Data collection

Method	Goal	Description
Literature analysis	<u>Contextualise the study</u> within the broader academic discourse and identify precise gaps that the current research aims to address.	Extensive literature review to identify existing knowledge and theoretical frameworks related to ULLs, sustainable mobility, and the 15-minute city concept, specifically focused on knowledge transfer and replication.
Survey	<u>Analyse current tools and solutions</u> related to urban proximity within a broad number of ULLs in terms of replication, as well as gain insights into the replication methodologies and existing practices.	Survey within the LLs network specifically focused on replication and knowledge transfer, including such elements as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience and methods for knowledge transfer • Barriers for replication • Potentials and successful examples of replication

In-depth semi-structured interviews	<u>Gain deeper insights</u> into the experiences and perspectives of different stakeholders involved in ULLs.	About 10 in-depth interviews will be conducted. The interviews are semi-structured, allowing for flexibility in exploring specific themes while ensuring consistency in the data collected across different cases.
Use-case design	<u>Develop detailed examples</u> of ULLs in diverse cities from multiple countries around Europe – Switzerland, Finland, Italy, Spain, Belgium, Netherlands and Turkey (Yin, 2009).	Based on literature review, interviews and outcomes of international projects (Multination, oPEN Lab, 2ISECAP, MICAD), the use cases will provide a structured approach to documenting the methodologies, activities, and outcomes of ULLs in different contexts.

Table 2. Data analysis

Method	Goal	Description
Individual descriptive use-case analysis	<u>Summarise the key findings and identify unique characteristics</u> of each of the LLs.	Each use case will include a descriptive part and specific section focused on mechanisms and tools for knowledge transfer and replication, highlighting the unique characteristics and outcomes of each ULL.
Comparative cross-case analysis	Identify common patterns, differences, and best practices across the different cases, as well as highlight possible trends and exceptional examples.	Comparative analysis of the chosen use-cases, which will allow putting light on relevant common and divergent elements will be conducted horizontally. This part is designed to be specifically focused on replication and knowledge transfer.
Solutions mapping	Summarise and visualize results of the analytical part proposing attractive and structured representation of solutions for replication and knowledge transfer	Finally, most relevant elements identified based on the use-case individual and comparative analysis will be classified and mapped, allowing visual representation of outcomes.

The comparative analysis will be conducted using the framework presented by figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of comparative analysis framework

The overall methodological framework could be summarised and illustrated by figure 2.

Figure 2. Methodological path

Expected outputs

To support practitioners such as public authorities, Living Lab or project managers in effective replication of experimental solutions within ULLs, this research proposes a practical methods, actionable tools and success practices, as well as structured guidance aiming to adapt and scale successful initiatives in diverse urban contexts. The paper aims to underscore both the potential and challenges associated with the role of the ULLs in facilitating knowledge transfer and replicating experimental solutions for urban mobility and proximity. This study is expected to provide outcomes that contribute to both academic understanding and practical application of ULLs for replicating experimental solutions and methodologies relating to sustainable urban mobility and the 15-minute City model.

Practice-oriented contribution

Identification of promising tools and methods

The study will evaluate, and map existing tools, methods, and practices used within ULLs that have demonstrated potential for replication. This includes co-creation methodologies and tools, participatory governance models, open and digital platforms that support knowledge sharing and innovation diffusion.

Case-based insights and replication practices

Through selected case studies, the research will illustrate concrete examples of how ULLs have contributed to replicating solutions related to the 15-minute City and sustainable urban mobility. These use-cases will highlight the good practices, challenges encountered, and lessons learned.

Policy and strategic recommendations

The findings will draft recommendations for local, national, and international policymakers on how to better support cities and ULLs in their journey to sustainable urban transformation. This includes guidance on embedding replication frameworks into urban strategies and programmes.

Scientific-oriented contribution

Enhanced understanding of replication mechanisms

The research will provide a comprehensive analysis of how ULLs facilitate the replication of experimental solutions, particularly in the domains of sustainable mobility and urban proximity. It will identify the mechanisms, conditions, and stakeholder dynamics that enable or hinder replication across different urban contexts.

Framework for knowledge transfer

A conceptual framework will be developed to guide the transfer of knowledge and scaling of successful ULL interventions. This framework will cover such elements as development process, success factors, documentation methods, stakeholder engagement processes, and policy integration in ensuring the sustainability and adaptability of innovations.

Contribution to global urban networks

The study will explore how ULLs can serve as connectors between local experimentation and global sustainability agendas, such as those promoted by the Covenant of Mayors, CNCA, and C40 Cities. It will propose pathways for aligning local experimental initiatives with broader innovative ecosystems.

Discussion

While ULLs hold substantial promise in fostering knowledge exchange and replicating experimental solutions, this study aims to open a discussion focused on the potential barriers and opportunities that may influence these processes. These factors can emerge at multiple levels—structural, organisational, social, technological, and contextual—and should be carefully addressed to unlock the full replication potential of ULLs. Based on recent literature and the analysis of examples from European projects (oPEN Lab, 2ISECAP, SWEET Lantern, MICAD), the following axes could be explored in greater depth:

- The contextual nature of urban experimental solutions, which heavily rely on local conditions
- Topic-related issues, particularly concerning urban proximity and mobility, with potential relevance for other fields
- Lack of resources and capacity among key stakeholders

- Fragmented knowledge transfer across stakeholders, limiting accessibility for external actors
- Absence of structured processes for documenting good practices and lessons learned
- Inadequate governance and difficulties in aligning objectives among key stakeholders

By identifying and critically reflecting on existing barriers and potentials, this research aims to support the development of a more robust and actionable replication framework that benefits practitioners. Addressing these challenges requires deliberate strategies, including context-sensitive adaptation, the development of easily applicable tools, and strengthened multi-stakeholder coordination. Future work will also explore enablers of successful replication and the role of policy alignment, as well as mechanisms for embedding replication into broader strategies.

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